

Rapid surface water warming and impact of the recent (2013 – 2016) temperature anomaly in shallow coastal waters at the eastern entrance of the Gulf of California

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Abstract

Surface seawater temperatures (SST) of the Northeastern Tropical Pacific are affected by seasonal, interannual (El Niño – Southern Oscillation), and decadal variabilities (Pacific Decadal Oscillation). Furthermore, anthropogenically-induced global warming is increasing SST worldwide. In this work, we show a long-term (1973–2013) SST time-series in a coastal site at the eastern entrance of the Gulf of California (Mazatlan, Mexico), determine the long-term warming trend, and examine the impact of the 2013-2016 North Pacific temperature anomaly. Variability analysis was focused on the period 2007–2016, for which a 10-year climatology was established. During this period, two La Niña and El Niño events, and an anomalous North Pacific warming event (“the Blob”) occurred. There was a clear correlation between the Oceanic Niño Index (ONI) and SST anomalies. La Niña events caused large negative anomalies (up to ~ 4 °C) in maximum temperatures, and El Niño events caused large positive anomalies (up to ~ 7 °C) in the minimum temperatures. The 2012-2013 Blob was preceded by an unreported anomalous regional warming at the entrance of the Gulf of California, which caused minimum temperature anomalies of ~ 4 °C. Since then, each winter has reflected increasing minimum temperature anomalies until reaching a ~ 7 °C maximum in 2016. These minimum temperature increases were caused by i) the inhibition of coastal upwelling of cold waters, and ii) a limited southwards penetration of cold California Current waters. By using monthly SST during the period 1973–2013 (40 years), we estimated a warming trend of 0.57 ± 0.01 °C per decade, which is larger than the global ocean trend. This relatively fast warming rate could be caused by i) local effects caused by

shallowness and coastal dynamics, ii) changes in the main currents that influence the area, and iii) global warming, as increasing surface temperatures can induce stronger thermoclines that last for longer, especially in regions commonly affected by upwelling events. If this trend persists, warming could have profound effects on the coastal ecosystems, which merits urgent attention by scientists and coastal zone managers.

Keywords: global warming, climate change, seawater, North Pacific

1. Introduction

The climate system is the result of complex interactions, mainly between solar radiation, atmosphere, oceans, terrestrial surface, and biota, which act at different temporal and spatial scales. At the inter-annual scale, the El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) phenomenon is the large-scale variability with the widest global climate influence (Carré *et al.*, 2014). Recent climate change, mainly caused by the anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases, has already caused global warming, thus also affecting climate both globally and inter-annually (Stocker *et al.*, 2013).

ENSO is a large-scale coupled ocean-atmosphere phenomenon with two phases (El Niño/La Niña) leading to positive/negative sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies (warm/cold phases) in the Eastern Tropical Pacific (ETP), with an irregular period between 2 and 7 years (Hanley *et al.*, 2003). The Walker circulation is caused by surface easterly winds from the ETP, raising warm air in the western Tropical Pacific (WTP), causing upper troposphere westerly winds, and sinking cold air in the ETP (Lau and Yang, 2003). During La Niña phase, warm waters are present in the WTP, and cold waters in the ETP, leading to a strong Walker circulation. The

presence of positive temperature anomalies in the ETP weaken the tropical Walker circulation by reducing the intensity of the easterlies and triggering the Bjerknes positive feedback mechanism by which warm waters of the WTP are transported to the ETP, which further reduces the Walker circulation and leads to an El Niño phase (Bjerknes, 1969). El Niño conditions may be terminated by negative feedbacks (for a comprehensive description of the ENSO phenomenon and the theories to explain its behaviour, the reader is referred to Wang et al., 2017).

The Gulf of California (GoC) is a subtropical semi-enclosed basin with a free entrance to the ETP (Lavin and Marinone, 2003). It is a long basin (1 200 km) of variable width (90-222 km; Páez-Osuna et al., 2016) and is surrounded by desert and semi-desert environments (Álvarez-Borrego, 1983). Broadly speaking, the circulation can be summarized as an outflow in the upper 200 m, an inflow below, and a surface layer that shows a strong seasonality (Lavin and Marinone, 2003).

ENSO dominates interannual ocean climate in the GoC (Baumgartner and Christensen, 1985; Lavin and Marinone, 2003). The main mechanisms are i) changes in the atmospheric circulation at mid-latitudes, and ii) coastal trapped waves, which transport the El Niño signal to higher latitudes (Herrera-Cervantes *et al.*, 2007). In the Gulf of California, ENSO events affect coastal upwelling and the pycnocline depth through coastal Kelvin waves (Herrera-Cervantes *et al.*, 2007), and therefore SST especially in the coastal areas (Lluch-Cota *et al.*, 2001; Herrera-Cervantes, *et al.*, 2007). On a longer time scale, the North Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO) also affects the GoC by causing stronger winter winds (Bernal et al., 2001).

Since October 2013, a large temperature anomaly was observed in the Gulf of Alaska (Peterson et al., 2015), named “the Blob” and attributed to a large sea level

pressure (SLP) anomaly across the region (Bond et al., 2015). This persisted during 2014 and most of 2015, and it was not related to ENSO but resembled modes of the North Pacific decadal variability (Di Lorenzo and Mantua, 2016). In the California Current System, warming was related to weak winds unrelated to ENSO (Robinson, 2016). In these already warm conditions, the “Godzilla” El Niño 2015-2016 developed in summer 2015, and maximum temperature anomalies were observed in the California Peninsula in October 2015 (Cavole et al., 2016). In fact, the 2015 temperature anomaly in the region might have been the precursor of the 2015-2016 El Niño (Tseng et al., 2017). Large SST and sea surface height were also observed in GoC during 2014-2016 (Frawley et al., 2019).

Recent climate change adds a long-term trend on climate variability (Stocker *et al.*, 2013). Between 1880 and 2012 the global surface temperature has increased by 0.85 ± 0.20 °C, the upper ocean has absorbed at least 60% of the net increase of energy in the climate system between 1971 and 2010, and SST has increased by 0.11 ± 0.02 °C per decade (Stocker *et al.*, 2013). However, this trend is not homogenous and its impacts are different at each region and ecosystem (Trenberth *et al.*, 2007), thus regional estimations are needed to establish proper adaptation and mitigation measures.

Coastal zones include complex and fragile ecosystems under many anthropogenic pressures, which make them especially vulnerable to climate change impacts. For example, increasing SST enhances sea level rise and changes the distribution and abundance of relevant ecosystems, such as mangroves and seagrass meadows (e.g. Wong *et al.*, 2014; Pörtner *et al.*, 2014; Páez-Osuna *et al.*,

2016), affects globally phytoplankton production (Behrenfeld et al., 2006), and causes population shifts (Pinsky et al., 2013).

Studying climate variability and trends in coastal regions is essential to improve the adaptation capacity and resilience of coastal human populations (Wong *et al.*, 2014). The objective of this work was to quantify SST warming trends in recent decades and to study its evolution during the last SST anomaly in the North Pacific (2013 – 2016). The methodology can be used in other coastal zones with enough data, and we expect that results will be useful to scientists and, especially, coastal zone managers worldwide.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area

The coastal zone of Mazatlán, Mexico (NE Pacific; Fig. 1), is at the entrance of the GoC (from Cabo San Lucas to Cabo Corrientes; Lavin and Marinone, 2003). It is characterized by the seasonal presence of a southward branch of the California Current and the northward Mexican Coastal Current (Godínez et al., 2010). The seasonality of the North-American monsoon and the fact that the basin is mostly flanked by mountain chains, cause that GoC winds mostly blow from the NW during winter and spring, causing strong upwelling during winter in the eastern side (cooler waters) and favouring the presence of cold California Current waters (Godínez et al., 2010). During summer, the region is influenced by weaker southeastern winds and the presence of warm tropical surface waters (Lavin and Marinone, 2003).

2.2. Data collection

We obtained the instrumental SST data used in this work from two time series (Fig. 1): (1) the *Recalada* time series, one of the monitoring stations at the Coastal Observatory of Mazatlán (Sanchez-Cabeza et al., 2018), with observations each 30 min (Hobo Conductivity logger U24-002) from 2013 to 2016 (all data were qualified and validated), and (2) the *Venados* time series, with 32 years (1973–2005) of manual (mercury thermometer) monthly observations, and an instrumental record (3-hourly data) collected with an autonomous sensor (HOBO Water Temp Pro v2) from 2005 to 2016. Because the time series had temporal gaps, we used reanalysis and model data to complete the data sets from (1) ERA-Interim (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts, ECMWF), which provides data since 1979 every 3 hours (Dee et al., 2011); and (2) *Phy_001_024* (European Earth Observation Programme–Copernicus, henceforth Copernicus), with daily data since 2006-12-27 (Copernicus, 2017). In both cases, we used the nearest data cell to Mazatlán Bay (Fig. 1). A summary of the time series used in this work is in Table S1.

As an indicator of El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO), we used the Oceanic Niño Index (ONI), which is the 3-month running mean of SST anomalies in the Niño 3.4 region (5°N–5°S, 120°–170°W). El Niño/La Niña phenomena are present when the index is higher/lower than 0.5°C during five consecutive months (NOAA, 2017).

Fig. 1. Study area and stations of SST time series. See text for a full description.

2.3. Data analysis

Climatological normals for environmental variables can be established when at least 30 years of data are available (WMO, 2017), but SST time series of this length are scarce. Instead, provisional normals can be established with time series of at least 10 years and can be used for climate analysis within that period (Trewin, 2007).

The monthly Venados time series (1973–2005) could not be used to establish operational normals as the sampling frequency was not adequate. Therefore, we used the instrumental Venados time series (2007–2016) to establish a 10-year provisional normal. We completed the gaps of the instrumental Venados time series (10% of the total period) with the Copernicus time series, which showed a high

correlation ($\rho = 0.97$, $p\text{-value} < 2.2 \cdot 10^{-16}$). We named this new SST time series as Reference time series (Fig. 2), which we used to establish the provisional normals (Table S2). Due to the lack of normality, we used the median (or 50th percentile) as a central SST indicator. The two-sided confidence interval ($\alpha=0.05$) was estimated using the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles, which were used as robust indicators of minimum and maximum SST. We performed all data manipulations and calculations with the statistical package R (R core team, 2018).

To study the relation between SST and the 2013-2016 temperature anomaly in Mazatlán Bay, we estimated the SST monthly deviations of the instrumental Venados and Recalada time series from the monthly provisional normals. Finally, we used the Spearman correlation coefficient to estimate the relation between the deviations and ONI.

We estimated the SST trend during the period 1973–2013 (40 years) in Mazatlán Bay by using the full Venados monthly time series. Data gaps (~6%) were completed with data from ERA-Interim, which showed a positive Spearman correlation with the full Venados time series ($\rho = 0.67$, $p\text{-value} < 2.2 \cdot 10^{-16}$). Finally, the trend was estimated from the linear regression of a smoothed line, calculated by local polynomial regression fitting (Cleveland *et al.*, 1992) with the R function `loess` (span = 0.75).

3. Results

3.1. Provisional normals and ENSO effects

ONI and the monthly deviations of the Reference time series from the provisional normals (Fig. 3, Table S2) showed a significant positive correlation (Fig. 4). The largest deviations were observed for the 2.5th percentile during the second half of each year, especially during El Niño events.

Fig. 2. Reference SST time series in Mazatlán Bay (2007-2016).

Fig. 3. Monthly provisional normals (2007 – 2016) in Mazatlán Bay, México.

Table 1. Spearman correlations between ONI and monthly deviations of the Recalada and full Venados time series from monthly provisional normals.

Time series parameter	Rho (ρ)	<i>p</i> -value	Number of data
Recalada percentile 2.5	0.50	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ ***	39
Recalada percentile 97.5	0.55	$3.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ ***	39
Recalada median	0.46	$3.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ ***	39
Venados percentile 2.5	0.58	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-12}$ ***	120
Venados percentile 97.5	0.54	$8.7 \cdot 10^{-11}$ ***	120
Venados median	0.65	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-16}$ ***	120

*** Significant at the 99.9% level.

Fig. 4. Monthly deviations of the time series from the provisional normals: A) 97.5th percentile, B) median, C) 2.5th percentile. D) ONI index: blue shadows (negative ONI) show La Niña 2007–2008 and 2011–2012 events, and red shadows (positive ONI) show El Niño 2009–2010 and 2015–2016 events.

3.2. Estimation of trends

As trends estimated during short periods can be strongly sensitive to the conditions at the beginning and the end of the series (Stocker *et al.*, 2013), we limited the trend analysis to the period 1973–2013, intentionally removing the period 2014–2016 likely affected by the Blob (2014-2015) and the strong El Niño 2015–2016. The estimated SST trend in Mazatlán Bay for the period from 1973 to 2013 was 0.57 ± 0.01 °C per decade. The trend is significant, with a p-value $\ll 0.05$ and $R^2 = 0.97$; Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Estimated trend of SST in Mazatlán Bay, between 1973 and 2013. The period 2014-2016 was intentionally removed to avoid a possible effect of the 2014-2016 temperature anomaly at the entrance of the Gulf of California.

4. Discussion

4.1. Effect of the ENSO phenomenon

During the period for which provisional normals were established, two El Niño events (2009–2010 and 2015–2016), two La Niña events (2007–2009 and 2010–2012), and the Blob (2013-2014) occurred. During La Niña 2007-2009, both the median and 97.5th percentile (used as an indicator of the maximum temperatures) showed large negative deviations (~ 4 °C), mirroring the ONI minima in both winters periods, with a larger minimum in 2008. The contrary was observed during the 2009-2010 El Niño event when the effect on the median and 97.5th percentile was neutral, but the effect on the 2.5th percentile (used as an indicator of minimum temperatures) was large (~ 6 °C), in agreement with the fact that el Niño SST impacts are largest during winter.

Again, during the strong La Niña 2010-2012 largest negative anomalies were observed for the median and 97.5th percentile, mirroring the ONI index, and slightly positive anomalies were observed for the 2.5th percentile, especially in mid-2011. During 2012-2013, neither the median nor the 97.5th percentile showed important changes, but the 2.5th percentile showed a large (~ 4 °C) positive deviation, lower but close to that observed in the 2009-2010 El Niño. This was surprising because it was not caused by ENSO nor PDO (both indices were close to zero), nor by the Blob, first detected in late 2013. Higher temperatures at the entrance of the GoC during the 2012-2013 winter might have been caused by mesoscale phenomena (eddies) blocking the arrival of CC waters to the GoC entrance (Castro et al., 2017).

Since this 2012-2013 regional event, the 2.5th percentile annual minima showed increasing values, corresponding to the 2013-2014 Blob and the 2014-2016

El Niño (one of the most intense registered events; Kogan & Guo, 2016), being maximum in the 2015-2016 winter (maximum anomaly ~ 7 °C). This was also reflected in the median values, but not in the maximum temperatures.

Overall, these observations show that the largest effects of ENSO on SST at Mazatlán Bay are caused by El Niño events, which markedly increase winter temperatures. Indeed, the Reference time series (Fig. 2) shows rather stable maxima (ranging from 30–32 °C), while minimum temperatures are more variable (ranging 15–20 °C). The main mechanisms by which El Niño can affect Mazatlán Bay SST include i) advection of coastal-trapped waves from the equator, and ii) changes in the atmospheric circulation at mid-latitudes (Lluch-Cota *et al.*, 2001; Herrera-Cervantes *et al.*, 2007; Turi *et al.*, 2018). Equatorial Kelvin waves are deflected to higher latitudes when reaching the coastal zone and advect heat and increase the thermocline depth in coastal areas, thus enhancing warming. As during La Niña events the thermocline depth is shallower, SST warming is not favoured.

In the Northeast Pacific, northeastern winds are the main cause of coastal upwelling (Emery and Hamilton, 1985; Latif and Barnett, 1994; Herrera-Cervantes *et al.*, 2007; Turi *et al.*, 2018). As El Niño events decrease northeastern winds (Fiedler and Mantua, 2017), they inhibit the upwelling of deep cold water, thus increasing annual minimum temperatures. Conversely, La Niña events enhance northeastern winds, thus increasing the occurrence of coastal upwelling events and decreasing SST temperature (Yuan and Yamagata, 2014).

Both mechanisms (Kelvin waves and modulation of northern winds) influence coastal upwelling and the thermocline depth, which modulate the contribution of deeper and cooler water. Therefore, these effects have a larger influence on the

coastal zone than in the open sea (Lluch-Cota *et al.*, 2001, Herrera-Cervantes *et al.*, 2007). This could explain why the SST absolute deviations in Mazatlán Bay are larger (~ 7 °C) than in the Gulf of California (~ 4 °C, Lavín & Marinone, 2003).

4.2. Fast warming

During the 1973–2013 period, specially chosen to avoid the strong 2014–2016 El Niño, the warming rate was 0.57 ± 0.01 °C per decade. If the full-time series was used (1973–2016), this trend would be sensibly larger (0.692 ± 0.005 °C per decade). Some similar trends are reported for meteorological stations in the Baja California Peninsula, such as La Paz (Martínez-Austria and Jano-Pérez, 2021).

The estimated warming trend is significantly higher than the average warming for the global and northern hemisphere SST, of 0.11 ± 0.02 °C per decade (1971–2010; Rhein *et al.*, 2013), indicating that SST in Mazatlán Bay is experiencing much faster warming than the global average. Although this observation is similar to the reported warming trend of 1.6 °C over 17 years (1984–2000) in the Gulf of California (0.7 °C per decade; Lavín *et al.*, 2003), in other cases no trend is found (Lluch-Cota *et al.*, 2010), or even a modest cooling trend was observed during 20 to 25 years (Lluch-Cota *et al.*, 2013).

This large warming trend may be due to i) local effects caused by the shallowness of the Mazatlan continental shelf and coastal dynamics, ii) changes in the currents that influence the area, such as the California Current, which supplies cold water to the zone, and the Mexican Coastal Current, which contributes with warm waters, and iii) global warming, as increasing surface temperatures induce stronger thermoclines that last for longer, which decrease vertical mixing (such as the common upwelling events in the region) and promote SST increases. Whether

these and/or other processes are responsible for the fast warming rates observed, the fact is that between 1973 and 2016 the mean temperature has already increased by more than 2 °C, and if the trend is maintained, by 2100 it will be about 7 °C warmer than in 1973. The impacts of such an increase are difficult to estimate but certainly would have profound changes in the coastal ecosystems (ranging from deoxygenation to species displacement) and the environmental services that they provide. For example, local winds and temperature played a key role in the intra-annual and annual patterns of diversity and benthic dynamics in Mazatlán Bay (Carballo *et al.*, 2008).

5. Conclusions

Multi-decadal SST time-series from Mazatlán (México, entrance of the Gulf of California) were used to study long-term SST trends and the impact of ENSO events on coastal waters. We established provisional normals of SST for Mazatlán for the period 2007–2016. Although a long time series of 43 years was available, a climatological normal (minimum 30 years) was not feasible because of its low temporal resolution (1 month). The distribution parameters (percentiles 2.5 and 97.5, and median) were useful SST indicators of minimum, maximum and average values.

ENSO had a strong influence on SST variability in Mazatlán Bay, especially on winter temperatures, since El Niño events increased minimum temperatures by 4–7 °C, whereas La Niña events decreased ~ 4 °C maximum temperatures. The fact that the largest anomalies occurred in winter suggests that changes in regional atmospheric conditions (such as wind direction and intensity) modify the occurrence and intensity of coastal upwelling.

The positive and significant trend of SST in Mazatlán Bay during the last 4 decades (1973–2013: 0.57 ± 0.01 °C per decade) indicates that the warming rate in this area is larger than the world average. This could be due to local effects of coastal morphology and dynamics, changes in main currents affecting this area, and the formation of a stronger and longer-lasting thermocline that would promote SST warming. In any case, if the observed warming rate persists, this could have profound effects on the coastal ecosystem, which merit urgent attention by scientists and coastal zone managers.

Supporting information

Supporting information includes:

- Table S1. Description of the time series used in this work.
- Table S2. Provisional normals for Mazatlán Bay (2007–2016).
- File *SST venados 1973 - 2016.csv*: Venados SST time series.
- File *SST reference 2007 - 2016.csv*: Reference SST time series.

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Data statement

Data are provided as supplementary information.

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